

Moderating Effects of Government Policies on the Antecedents of Occupational Safety and Health of Police Officers in Nairobi City County, Kenya

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Abstract

The main study was entitled: Antecedents of Occupational Safety and Health among the Police Officers in Nairobi City County in Kenya. The subject of the paper is only based on one variable, government policies, practices and procedures. The objective or purpose was to determine on the moderating effects of government policies, practices and procedures on the antecedents of occupational, safety and health of police officers. The unit of study was police officers and Nairobi City County was chosen to collect data for it is the city headquarters of Kenya. The target population was 4,000 officers which included commanders. In this study, a sample size of 200 (5%) police officers was chosen through simple random sampling. In Nairobi, some 33 police stations were identified for the study and an initial 10% were picked for a pilot study. For the remaining, a sample of 5 percent of police officers and a commanding officer in each station were studied. Data from the respondents were collected by the use of questionnaires as a tool of study from the officers who were on duty but after permission had been sought from relevant authorities. Every officer commanding a police station was chosen. Each respondent was given an explanation on the importance of the study which was done freely with their willingness, at a convenient location. Each respondent was requested to confirm in writing, affirmative action or by signing a document without indicating their name to show that the study was done with their approval. The filled questionnaires were collected and kept with confidence. Through these modes of data collection, every population was well represented as a sample. The study used Cronbach Alpha Coefficient to test on the reliability of instruments. The validity of the research instruments was also tested. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in data analysis using SPSS version 20. Data was then presented in the form of figures, tables and charts. Through factor analysis, all the eight statements of a variable under study were retained for they were above 0.5. The response rate of the respondents was 75.5% which is acceptable. Majority of the police officers, 42.4% were of the view that government policies are helpful to them during emergencies. Reliability analysis was tested on the variable government policies using Cronbach Alpha and it had a value of .787 which was greater than .7 showing reliability. In addition to the KMO test, the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was also significant (.000, at $p < .05$) for all the study variables including government policies. These results provided an outstanding validation for further statistical analysis which was conducted. All the statements on government policies had a factor loading values which were greater than .5 and were therefore accepted and thus no sub variable was dropped. Results also

showed that the R squared after moderation by government policies was .903 thus higher than the non-moderated effect which had its R square being .828. It means that government policies, practices and procedures moderates the relationship between leadership style, legal framework, nature of work environment, available resources and work load and occupational, safety and health of police officers explain 90.3% of the variations in occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya.

Key Words: Government Policies, Practices and Procedures, Police Officers, Occupational, Safety and Health

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Problem

In a study which was done on policies, it was found out that they are critical for the smooth running of organizations (Nzuve & Njeru, 2013). They stated that policies of organizations should clearly be stated and defined well. In their research, these scholars found out that 82 percent of the respondents recorded that when policies are not clear, they will affect the way employees performed their tasks. This is quite relevant when it comes to the occupational, safety and health of employees. It was also found out in this study that only 3 percent of the respondents were not sure if policies could affect performance. This was a small percentage as compared to those who felt it did affect. It is the responsibility of police officers to cooperate with other government institutions (Hope, 2015). The scholar argued that police officers were established through various Acts and they play different roles for the success of policing. In a survey that was done, 47 percent of police officers and 89 percent of those in charge were satisfied with their jobs (Transparency International Kenya, 2016).

1.2 Specific Objective

- i. Determine on the moderating effects of government policies, practices and procedures on the antecedents of occupational, safety and health of police officers.

1.3 Study Hypothesis

$H_{A_{vi}}$: There is no significant moderating relationship between government policies, practices, procedures & occupational, safety and health among police officers in Kenya.

2.0 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Economic Model

David Ricardo was an economics scholar in the period 1700 to 1800. It was in 1817 that this academician posited on the concept of comparative advantage and presented it in 1885 (Abbas & Muhammed, 2016). In 2007, Myrdal claimed that Ricardo's theory was based on natural law, dealt with economic problems and also used the same concepts in the studies. The scholar further stated that Adam Smith pioneered in economic theory. The theory is valuable for the good running of an economy (Basu, 2013). This researcher added that if a target group is susceptible to a lifestyle like too many injuries at work then that one has to be factored in.

It has been found out through studies that when organizations run their businesses to profitability, it meant that they had resourceful employees (Nunez & Villanueva, 2011). They added that the safety and health of employees are not valued by most organizations. Thomson (1997) had argued that when a work place is safe and workers are also safe and healthy, it will mean they have a competitive advantage for a company. That safe environment will lead to a high production, making employees joyful and unnecessary costs are cut. Basu (2013) argued that people live in a world of abstract economic model, policy and politics. This scholar claimed that it is not like rocket science or any other scientific study which people can easily understand, for example, mathematical formulas (Basu, 2013). This scholar stated that the problem with policies is that people design them with hidden agendas. They argue further that they may like to benefit at the end of it all but not the users. This is where corruption comes in and political manipulations (Basu, 2013). Downs (1957) argued that a government should be persuaded by her citizens on the best police policies which should be beneficial to the majority of them.

Basu (2013) argued that due to world economic upheavals, organizations and even countries strive to come up with favorable policies for employees and a populace. This scholar posited that trade unions have to negotiate with governments. Their aim is to ensure that their members benefit when doing collective bargaining agreements (CBAs). In most cases, the labor market does not favor employees but instead the employers. Basu (2013) claimed that the labor market is not operating well but has instead failed. The scholar recommended for the need to reform labor laws which would catalyze the growth of a nation. It will lead to enhancing business growth which will eventually be beneficial to all workers in an economy. It is added that a good economic theory in making markets stable will mean purchasing more food and stock from the populace especially during huge harvests which lead to low pricing and vice versa. The

economic model supports the variable government policies, practices and procedures which should be developed to make the police force have a comparative advantage in their operations and their occupational safety and health.

2.2 Government Policies, Practices and Procedures

Organizations doing business will perform well depending on the type of leadership style and the appropriate policies which are in operation (Alsheikh, Abdulraheem, Halim, & Alremawi, 2017). They posited that the findings of this Australian research showed that company policies affected the processes which are operational in hotels and the way they are undertaken by employees and their performance. They added that it has an effect in terms of their commitment, norms, and values which should be in agreement with those of their organization. As a result, these will catalyze the employees and will eventually meet their set targets or goals and objectives (Alsheikh et al., 2017).

The policies which a company have has an effect on how work is supposed to be done in all aspects of their dealings in terms of attendance, its quality standards and production levels (Kuranchi-Mensah & Amponsah-Tawaiah, 2016). They added that each of the companies in operation has their own business cultures and how things are done which come in as a form of policies. A company's culture is just like police policies which is a moderating effect in this study. The nature of leadership styles, for example, transformational or transactional has an effect on employee performance (Asheikh et al., 2017). They posited that these types of leadership styles have a positive effect and negative effects respectively to long-term performance.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for the study is shown below in figure 2.1. It outlines all the variables which were handled in the study which included the independent, moderating and dependent variables. In this paper, it is only the moderating variable government policies, practices and procedures which are under study.

Independent Variables

Moderating Variable

Dependent Variables

Source: Author, 2021

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework.

2.4 Empirical Studies

2.4.1 Government Policies, Practices and Procedures

In another research carried out across 65 countries, it was recommended that safety was important for it was better to do prevention than to cure (Sweden International Development Agency, 2013). In this research, it was stated that employment injury schemes performed three linked functions. It was further reported that they helped in the support of prevention at work so that fewer work place accidents take place and fewer workers are affected by occupational diseases. Where accidents and illness will have occurred, they help in the rehabilitation process, so that the individuals affected can when possible return to their original jobs, or when this is not possible then move to another employment (Sweden International Development Agency, 2013). They offered compensation to individual workers who might have lost out through illness or disability.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Mkansi and Acheampong (2012) defined that a research design is a study that is descriptive in nature. Black (2003) claims that doing a research requires a lot of skill so as to design ways of carrying out studies. This scholar added that the research has to be designed in ways which include mentioning the instruments being used. A research design will show the hypothesis or hypotheses, the variables involved that are both dependent and independent (Mkansi & Acheampong (2012). The design also will show if the study will be in form of experiments or exploratory. In this study, a descriptive survey design and explanatory was adopted.

3.2 Target Population

Zikmund, Babin, Carr, Adhikari, and Griffin (2013) defined that a target population has the units which are relevant to a study or where a sample shall be taken from. It may be in form of all registered persons a researcher is interested in, for example, a team of sales persons whose number is known. These are the elements which one will extract a sample from. Zikmund et al., (2013) stated that a population is a body of persons or items which have similar behaviors or way of doing things.

3.3 Sampling Frame, Sample and Sampling Technique

3.3.1 Sampling Frame

Zikmund et al., (2013) defined a sampling frame as the items where a sample is derived from. There are conditions necessary for any research to be successful. It is argued by Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) that the information which is availed in a sampling frame contributes to the accuracy of any findings derived through research.

3.3.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

Zikmund et al., (2013) defined a sample as part of what makes up a whole body of items. Samples are considered small size if they are less than or equal to 30 as argued by Khandelwal (2011). Such a study shall use the t-distribution. The above author adds that in situations where sample sizes are small, t-test, F-test, and Chi-squares are used. These are used for hypothesis testing. The Chi-squares are quite useful for both small and big samples (Khandelwal, 2011). Julious (2005) stated that it is important for all studies to provide a sample size which is a requirement. This is to do with the accuracy of a study, mean, variance and other regulations on research. It is added further that scholars indicate this for further use by other researchers doing a similar study. Nassa et al., (2016) advocated a sample size of 20% when a population is many hundreds, 10% if a few thousands and 5% or less if several thousands (quoting from Nwana, 1981). It is advocated that a sample size can be calculated using a percentage (Nwana, 1982). The study used the later, that is, 5%, 200 police officers since the target population size was approximately 4,000 as provided by relevant authorities.

Anderson, Sweeney, and Williams (2012) claimed that there are several tests which are used in studying populations. There is the goodness of fit test. This is normally used when with multinomial populations. Here the authors argue that we have to consider a situation where each element of a population is assigned one or more classes. A population like that is called multinomial. An experiment is undertaken where each is assumed to be independent. For each outcome, its probabilities remain the same for every experiment done. In situations where we are undertaking a goodness of fit, this is aimed at getting a sample in a study.

Other tests as argued by Anderson et al., (2012) included test of independence. This is also a chi-square distribution where the sample data is used to test independence of two variables. Each sample is chosen and they are asked some research questions. This was not relevant in this study since we have many variables. Another test is the goodness of fit which is called Poisson meaning it is under normal distribution. Here the population is hypothesized. This is

where clients, for example, are monitored as they arrive at intervals of five minutes. It is used to arrive at the sample.

Sampling technique is a method which is used by researchers to arrive at a sample (Zikmund et al., 2013). It is a skill which is being used to get the sample size of a study. These authors list several types of sampling techniques which are simple random, systematic, stratified, cluster and multistage.

3.4 Data collection instruments

These are instruments which are used to collect data during a study, for example, a questionnaire as a tool.

3.4.1 Primary and secondary data

These are data which are readily available from primary sources like interviews or from publications like in academic journals, books, the internet or books.

3.6 Data Collection Procedures

3.6.1 Pilot Testing

Julious (2005) posits that there is the rule of thumb to use a sample size of 12 percent of a group when doing a pilot study. The study used 10% for a pilot study in the police stations sampled. The author argues further that: when designing a critical trial on appropriate justification for the sample size, it should be provided for in the protocol. However, there are a number of settings when undertaking a pilot trial when there is no prior information to base a sample size on. For such studies the recommendation is a sample size of 12 percent per group. The justifications for this sample size are based on the rationale about feasibility, precision about the mean and variance; and regulatory considerations. The context of the justifications is that future studies will use the information from the pilot in their design. Johnson and Gordon (2010) argued that pilot studies are done prior to the main study in order to iron out some issues like scales, instruments of research, items to be chosen, consistency, estimation of parameters and response rates. The pilot study in addition was useful in correcting any errors in the questionnaires.

3.6.2 Reliability and Validity of Instruments

Tavakol and Dennick (2011) advocated on the use of Cronbach Alpha for it is used to test on the internal consistency of items being used. They stated that they should be between values of 0 to 1. When it falls on 0.8, it will show reliability unlike 0.36 which shows existence of an error. The study can carry out a research on a few respondents of a sample.

3.7 Data analysis and presentation

After data has been collected, it has to be analyzed. Levine, Krehbiel and Berenson (2007), stated that the slope of Y (which is $\beta_0 = Y$ intercept) holds the variables constant. The model was useful in trying to do analysis on the correlation of the variables.

4.0 RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

4.1 Reliability

The instruments used must be reliable for the study to be a good research for proper analysis.

Table 1.0: Reliability Analysis

Variable	Number of items	Cronbach alpha	Comments
Government Policies	8	.787	Reliable

Source: Author, 2021

4.2 Validity

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) was used to determine whether the responses generated were valid based on their values. For a data set to be regarded as valid and appropriate for statistical analysis, the value of KMO should be greater than .5 (Field, 2013). The results of the KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (significance) are summarized in Table 2.0.

Findings in Table 2.0 show that the KMO statistic for all the variables (leadership style, legal framework, work environment, available resources, work load, government policies and Occupational, Safety and health) were greater than .5 which was significantly high; that is greater than the critical level of significance of the test which was set at .5 (Field, 2013). In addition to the KMO test, the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was also significant (.000, at $p < .05$) for all the study variables. These results provided an outstanding validation for further statistical analysis which was conducted.

Table 2.0: Validity Test

Variable	KMO	Significance
Government Policies	.619	.000

Source: Author, 2021

4.3 Demographic

4.3.1 Gender Characteristics

Based on the tabulated results of the study, majority (62.9%) of the respondents were males while 37.1% were females. The results imply that most of the police officers in the Kenyan police force are males. This could be as a result of the fact that for a long time in Kenya, the police force has been viewed as a men's profession and not women. In this study, the police force was seen as a man's job like other professions like aviation in the fuel industry which was found out through research in Democratic Republic of the Congo (Nzuve & Kelwon, 2014).

4.4 Factor Analysis of Government Policies, Procedures, and Practices

4.4.1 Factor Loading for Government Policies

In this study, factor analysis was carried out on the statements for government policies which were the moderating variable. Tabachinick and Fidell (2007) affirmed that, variables with factor loading having Eigen values greater than .5 are considered good. The study's factor loading for government policies are presented in Table 3.0. Results on Table 3.0 show that all the statements on government policies had a factor loading values which are greater than .5. They were therefore accepted and thus no sub variable was dropped. The highest item on new laws, policies, practices, procedures and visions which led to new lifestyles had factor loading of .691. The lowest item on government policies, practices and procedures which are not implemented by authorities and not useful to police during emergency situations had a measure of .535. All the eight (8) items were therefore retained and used during further analysis.

Table 3.0: Factor Analysis for Government Policies

Statement	Factor Loading
Government Policies, Practices & Procedures help me to efficiently handle emergency situations	.551
Government Policies, Practices & Procedures are not implemented by authorities and are not useful to me during emergency situations	.535
When I have the qualifications I will then be promoted based on government policies, practices and procedures	.606
I will not smoothly rise through the ranks until retirement because of corruption	.633
I will at all times be compensated in case of injuries or accidents at work	.577
I will not be well compensated because my welfare and rights are normally ignored	.620
New laws, policies, practices, procedures and visions lead to new lifestyles	.691
When new laws, policies, practices, procedures and visions are developed, they will not help all stakeholders.	.647

Source: Author, 2021

4.5 Descriptive Statistics

4.5.1 Government Policies, Practices and Procedures

A government and its policies, practices and procedures was the moderating variable in the study. The study had sought to find out the moderating effects of government policies, practices and procedures on the antecedents of occupational, safety and health of police officers. A Likert scale of 1 to 5 (1 = Never, 2 = Seldom, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Almost Always) was used and the mean response rate from the respondents was calculated. The descriptive statistics for government policies are presented in Table 4.0.

The results in Table 4.0 indicate that a majority (42.40%) of the respondents indicated that government policies, practices and procedures are often helpful to them in efficiently handling emergency situations. The results show a mean of 3.50 with a standard deviation of .88. The results also show that (32.50%) of the respondents were of the opinion that sometimes government policies, practices and procedures were not implemented by authorities and were not useful to them during emergency situations. The results had a mean of 3.21 and a standard deviation of 1.13. In addition, the results show that (40.40%) of the respondents indicated that often when they had the qualifications they then get promoted based on government policies, practices and procedures. The results had a mean of 3.52 and standard deviation of .87.

The study results further show that most (37.10%) of the respondents indicated that they often do not smoothly rise through the ranks until retirement because of corruption. The results had a mean of 3.54 and a standard deviation of 1.03. In addition, the results show that (41.70%) of the respondents were of the opinion that they were at all times compensated in case of injuries or accidents at work. The results had a mean of 3.35 and standard deviation of .94. The study also shows that majority (41.1%) of the respondents were sometimes not well compensated because their welfare and rights are ignored. It had a mean of 3.25 and standard deviation of .99. Similarly, the results show that, majority (45.00%) of the respondents indicated that sometimes new laws, policies, practices, procedures and visions lead to new lifestyles. The results had a mean of 3.25 and standard deviation of 1.01. Finally, the results show that (37.20%) of the respondents indicated that often when new laws, policies, practices, procedures and visions are developed, they do not help all stakeholders. The results had a mean of 3.29 and standard deviation of 1.03. In general, the responses had an average mean and standard deviation of 3.36 and .99.

The above study agrees with another which was done in Romania. In that research, when risk management was done on occupational safety and health, it meant the management of policies, procedures and practices were used to identify risks (Achim, 2014). The scholar added that the risks of police officers include hazards they face at work, risks of the hazards, they look for the steps to control them and revise the same process. This academician posited further that the effects on the health of police officers include both physical and mental which arise from work. Other effects arise due to the kind of work done (shifts, poor feeding, lack of offs or rests, the use of force causing stress or tension, moral issues in using guns) (Achim, 2014). It is added that police officers are also affected by the strategies they use and consequences, hostility from clients, fear of mingling with criminals, threats of death, family influence and other pressures of work. In this research, it was found out that all the above effects lead to diverse diseases which include cardiovascular, digestive, osteo-articular system, endocrine and infectious and parasitic ailments (Achim, 2014).

Table 4.0: Government Policies

Statement	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Often	Almost Always	Mean	SD
Government Policies, Practices & Procedures help me to efficiently handle emergency situations	3.30%	6.00%	38.40%	42.40%	9.90%	3.50	.88
Government Policies, Practices & Procedures are not implemented by authorities and are not useful to me during emergency situations	6.60%	20.50%	32.50%	25.80%	14.60%	3.21	1.13
When I have the qualifications I will then be promoted based on government policies, practices and procedures	2.60%	6.00%	39.70%	40.40%	11.30%	3.52	.87
I will not smoothly rise through the ranks until retirement because of corruption	6.00%	5.30%	34.40%	37.10%	17.20%	3.54	1.03
I will at all times be compensated in case of injuries or accidents at work	4.60%	9.30%	41.70%	35.10%	9.30%	3.35	.94

I will not be well compensated because my welfare and rights are normally ignored	5.30%	13.90%	41.10%	30.50%	9.30%	3.25	.99
New laws, policies, practices, procedures and visions lead to new lifestyles	9.30%	5.30%	45.00%	31.80%	8.60%	3.25	1.01
When new laws, policies, practices, procedures and visions are developed, they will not help all stakeholders.	6.10%	14.90%	32.40%	37.20%	9.50%	3.29	1.03
Average						3.36	.99

Source: Author, 2021

4.5.2 Test for Linearity

Source: Author, 2021

Figure 3.0: Linearity

4.5.3 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted to ascertain the association between the study variable of government policies and occupational, safety and health. Pearson correlation for each of the variables was generated using SPSS. Correlation coefficient was computed and used to test whether there existed interdependency between independent variables and also whether the independent variables were related to the dependent variable. Scholars argued that correlation coefficients greater than .5 are strong, .3-.5 (moderate), and less than .3 (weak) (Heale & Twycross, 2015).

The results indicated that there was a strong positive and significant association between government policies and occupational, safety and health of police officers ($r=.913$, $P\text{-value}=.00$).

Table 5.0: Correlation Matrix

		Occupational Safety and Health	Leadership Style	Legal Framework	Work Environment	Available Resources	Work Load	Government Policy
Occupational, Safety and Health	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000						
Leadership Style	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.789**	1.000					
Legal Framework	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.683**	.515**	1.000				
Work Environment	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.721**	.590**	.509**	1.000			
Available Resources	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.722**	.677**	.486**	.553**	1.000		
Work Load	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.577**	-.438**	-.363**	-.392**	.505**	1.000	
Government Policy	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.913**	.709**	.606**	.681**	.678**	.396**	1.000

** Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author, 2021

4.6 Regression Analysis and Analysis of Variance

In this study, regression was used to find the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to show how the former explains the later.

4.6.1 Moderating Effect of Government Policies

The sixth objective of the main study had sought out on the moderating effect of government policies, practices and procedures on the antecedents of occupational, safety and health of police officers. All the independent variables were moderated by the variable government policies, practices and procedures to give composite variables.

i. Goodness of Fit for the Moderating Effect of Government Policies, Practices and Procedures

The results in Table 6.0 show the goodness of fit for the moderating effects of government policies, practices and procedures. The R squared was used to check how well the model fitted the data after moderation. The results in Table 6.0 show that the R squared after moderation by government policies, practices and procedures was .903 which was higher than the non-moderated effect which had its R square being .828. This means that government policies, practices and procedures moderates the relationship between leadership style, legal framework, nature of work environment, available resources and work load and occupational, safety and health of police officers and explain 90.3% of the variations in occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya.

Table 6.0: Model Fitness for the Moderating Effect of Government Policies

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.950 ^a	.903	.900	.21810

a. Predictors: (Constant), Workload*Government Policies, Available Resources* Government Policies, Legal Framework* Government Policies, Work Environment*Government Policies, Leadership Style*Government Policies

Source: Author, 2021

ii. ANOVA Analysis for the Moderating effect of Government Policies, Practices and Procedures

The results presented in Table 7.0 show the analysis of variance (ANOVA) results on the moderating effect of government policies, practices and procedures. The results in Table 7.0 confirm that the regression model of moderating effect of government policies, practices and procedures on the effects of the antecedents on occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya index is significant and supported by $F=269.770$, ($p<.000$) since p-values was .000 which is less than .05. The results affirm the importance of government policies, practices and procedures in occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya.

Table 7.0: ANOVA for the Moderating Effect of Government Policies

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	64.164	5	12.833	269.770	.000 ^b
	Residual	6.898	145	.048		
	Total	71.062	150			

a. Dependent Variable: Occupational, Safety and Health

b. Predictors: (Constant), Workload*Government Policies, Available Resources* Government Policies, Legal Framework* Government Policies, Work Environment*Government Policies, Leadership Style*Government Policies

Source: Author, 2021

iii. Regression coefficients analysis for the moderating Effect of Government Policies, Practices and Procedures

The results in Table 8.0 show the regression coefficients after moderation using government policies, practices and procedures. Based on the results in Table 8.0, leadership style was significant after moderation with P value $.000 < .05$. This implies that government policies, practices and procedures moderate the relationship between the leadership style and occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya. The results also show that legal framework was significant after moderation with P value $.000 < .05$. This implies that government policies, practices and procedures moderate the relationship between the legal framework and occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya.

The results further show that work environment was significant after moderation with P value $.000 < .05$. This implies that government policies, practices and procedures moderate the relationship between the work environment and occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya. The results in addition show that available resources was insignificant after moderation with P value $.015 < .05$. This implies that government policies, practices and procedures do not moderate the relationship between the available resources and occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya. Finally, the results show that work load was significant after moderation with P value $.001 < .05$. In addition to this the value of R squared increased from 82.8 before moderation to .903 after moderation. This implies that government policies, practices and procedures moderate the relationship between the work load and occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya.

Table 8.0: Moderating Effect of Government Policies, Practices and Procedures.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized T Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	1.452	.067		21.533	.000
Leadership Style*Government Policies	.055	.012	.326	4.607	.000
Legal Framework*Government Policies	.047	.009	.290	5.238	.000
1 Work Environment*Government Policies	.038	.010	.229	3.816	.000
Available Resources*Government Policies	.026	.011	.158	2.459	.015
Workload*Government Policies	-.016	.005	-.086	-3.315	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Occupational, Safety and Health

Source: Author, 2021

4.7 Hypothesis Testing

The sixth Hypothesis Tested was:

H_{Avi}: There is no significant moderating relationship between Government Policies, Practices, Procedures and Occupational, Safety and Health among Police Officers in Kenya.

The hypothesis was tested using a multiple linear regression and determined using p-value. The acceptance/rejection criterion was that, if the p value was less than .05, we do not reject the H_{Avi} but if it was more than .05, the H_{Avi} is rejected. Government policies, practices, procedures was a positive and significant moderating variable for leadership style .000<.05, legal framework .000<.05, work environment .000<.05, available resources .015<.05 and work load .001<.05. The alternative hypothesis was therefore not rejected. The study adopted the alternative hypothesis that there was a significant moderating relationship between government policies, practices, procedures and occupational, safety and health among police officers in Kenya.

5.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Discussion of Study

Government policies are of paramount importance. In a research done, women police officers strive very hard both physically and emotionally to fit in that man's force because government policy does not favor them (Langan, Sanders & Agocs, 2016). These scholars added that at times they get reassigned duties or demoted after their maternity leave for them to prove themselves. In a survey done by an organization, Afrobarometer, their research findings showed that also the relationship between civilians and police officers was wanting and it necessitated the opening up of customer relations desks in police stations to improve or enhance it (Afrobarometer, 2015). In this 2015 survey among civilians, it was discovered that 29.8% of Kenyan citizens did not trust police officers. The police in another survey on standards set by them, it contradicted these findings by showing that 98.2% of these officers did not see any issue they have with civilians (IPOA, 2013). Most of the studies done on police are done by themselves but civilians who dared into it are not provided with full information (Ruteere, 2014).

A study was done by Violanti et al., (2016) and the researchers handled on the hopelessness of police officers. They argued that hopelessness was caused by the fear of changes which can be either physical, or lack of leadership (administration and organizational) which can lead to suicides. This study was too narrow. In Tanzania, a study was done on violence which affects women who have to report to police officers (McCleary-Sills et al., 2013). In an IPOA study, the findings showed that the police population in Kenya was 80,000 in 2016 where 78.75% of them lived in very poor housing units but due to new recruitments caused by improved government policy, it reduced by 8% (IPOA, 2016). This study dwelt mostly on police officers' security, housing, government policies among others.

The study agrees with a research of military soldiers' hardiness as mediators in achieving their readiness. It was found by scholars that there are high levels of hardiness with a mean of 3.26 and standard deviation of .49 (Shinga & Dyk, 2015). They added that the correlation between soldiers' RWS ($P < .01$), RWU ($P < .01$) and hardiness ($P < .01$) are significantly related with CR. These are the soldiers' style of readiness, unit of belonging and hardiness or resistance to stress. CR (Combat Readiness) is the state at which a soldiers' mind affected their occupational safety and health. In the study, its findings also agree with other studies which showed that policies on operations, organization and reward systems of the police force are a cause of their

stress (Turker, 2015). In addition, when officers are trained on stress, it will make them to use services which reduce the same. Due to policy, 30 percent of women report violence (Lockwood & Prohaska, 2015).

5.2 Moderating Effect of Government Policies, Practices and Procedures

The sixth objective of the study was to find out the moderating effect of government policies, practices and procedures on the antecedents of occupational, safety and health of police officers. R squared after moderation by government policies, practices and procedures was .908 which was higher than the non-moderated effect which had its R square being .846. This meant that government policies, practices and procedures moderated the relationship between leadership style, legal framework, nature of work environment, available resources and work load and occupational, safety and health of police officers and explains 90.3% of the variations in occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya. In addition the results indicated that, leadership style was significant after moderation with P-value $.000 < .05$. This implies that government policies, practices and procedures moderate the relationship between the leadership style and occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya. The results also show that legal framework was significant after moderation with P value $.000 < .05$. This implies that government policies, practices and procedures moderate the relationship between the legal framework and occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya.

5.3 Summary of Hypothesis

Table 9.0: Summary of Hypotheses

Objective No.	Objective	Research Hypothesis	Rule p-value	Comment
Objective 6	To find out the moderating effects of Government Policies, Practices and Procedures on the antecedents of Occupational, Safety and health of police officers	H _{AVI} : There is no significant moderating relationship between Government Policies, Practices, Procedures and Occupational, Safety and Health among police officers in Kenya.	Reject H ₀₁ if p-value <.05 t-statistics > 1.96	The alternative hypothesis was not rejected; therefore, there is a significant moderating relationship between Government Policies, Practices, Procedures and Occupational, Safety and Health among police officers in Kenya.

Source:
Author, 2021

5.4 A Summary, Conclusion and Recommendation

The sixth objective of the study was to find out the moderating effect of government policies, practices and procedures on the antecedents of occupational, safety and health of police officers. Based on the findings, the study concludes that government policies, practices and procedures have a moderating effect on the relationship between leadership style, legal framework, nature of work environment, available resources and work load and occupational, safety and health of police officers in Kenya. In addition, the study concludes that, police officers in Kenya are promoted based on government policies, practices and procedures and only if the officers possess the required qualification. Finally, the study concludes that, police officers in Kenya are in most cases not well compensated because their welfare and rights are normally ignored by the government. It is recommended that a government should come up with good policies for it will determine the occupational safety of their police officers.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, S., & Muhammed, S.D. (2016). Pakistan's international competitiveness over Asia and Europe. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 10(2), 359-367.
- Achim, A.C. (2014). Risk management issues in policing: From safety risks faced by law enforcement agents to occupational health. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 15, 1671-1676. Retrieved on 17th September 2019 from [https://doi:10.1016/s2212-5671\(14\)00639-x](https://doi:10.1016/s2212-5671(14)00639-x)
- Afrobarometer (2015). Afrobarometer 2014/2015 survey of national attitudes in Kenya on democracy and governance issues. Retrieved on 2/12/2020 from <https://www.afrobarometer.org/online-data-analysis/analyzeonline>
- Alsheikh, G. A. A., Abdulraheem, A., Halim, M.S.B.A., & Alremawi, M.S.A. (2017). The mediating role of organizational culture on the relationship between employee performance and antecedents in the hotel sector. *Journal of Reviews on Global Economics*, 6, 489-497.
- American Psychological Association (2020). *Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association* (7th ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1037/0000165-000>
- Anderson, D.R., Sweeney, D.J. and Williams, T.A. (2012). *Quantitative methods for business*. Mason, USA: A South-Western Cengage Learning.
- Basu, K. (2013). Does economic theory inform government policy? *Millennial Asia*, 4(1), 27-39. New Delhi, India: SAGE Publications Private Limited.
- Black, T. R. (2003). *Doing quantitative research in the social sciences*. London: Sage Publications.
- Downs, A. (1957). An economic theory of political action in a democracy. *Journal of Political Economy*, 65(2), 135-150.
- Field, A. (2013). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics*. Sage.
- Heale, R., & Twycross, A. (2015). Validity and reliability in quantitative studies. *Evidence-Based Nursing, ebnurs*, 18(3), 66-67.
- Hope sr, K.R. (2015). In pursuit of democratic policing: An analytical review and assessment of police reforms in Kenya. *International Journal of Police Service and Management*, 17(2), 91-97. Retrieved on July 9th 2018 from <https://doi:10.1177/1461355715580915>
- Independent Policing Oversight Authority (IPOA) (2013). *Baseline Survey*.
- Independent Policing Oversight Authority (IPOA) (2016). *A Report on Housing*.

- Johnson, G.A. and Gordon, P. (2010). Initial scale developing sample size for pilot studies, Brooks, 70(3).
- Julious, S.A. (2005). Pharmaceutical statistics. The Journal of Applied Statistics in the Pharmaceutical Industry, 4(4), Oct/Dec.
- Khandelwal, A. (2011). Business statistics. Delhi: New Age International (P) Ltd., Publishers.
- Kuranchie-Mensah, E.B., & Amponsah-Tawiah, K. (2016). Employee motivation and work performance: A comparative study of mining companies in Ghana. Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management (JIEM), 9(2), 255-309.
- Langan, D., Sanders, C. B., & Agocs, T. (2017). Canadian police mothers and the boys' club: Pregnancy, maternity leave, and returning to work. Women & Criminal Justice, 27(4), 235-249.
- Levin, D. M., Krehbiel, T. C., & Berenson, M. L. (2007). Business statistics: A first course. Delhi: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Lockwood, D., & Prohaska, A. (2015). Police officer gender and attitudes toward intimate partner violence: How policy can eliminate stereotypes. International Journal of Criminal Justice Sciences, 10(1), 77-90.
- McCleary-Sills, J., Namy, S., Nyoni, J., Rweyemamu, D., Salvatory, A., & Steven, E. (2013). Help-seeking pathways and barriers for survivors of gender-based violence in Tanzania: Results from a study in Dar es Salaam, Mbeya, and Iringa regions. Dar es Salaam, Tanzania: Engender Health/Champion, 1-75. International Center for Research on Women (ICRW).
- Mkansi, M., & Acheampong, E.A. (2012). Research philosophy debates and classifications: Students' dilemma. The Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods, 10(2).
- Mugenda, O.M., and Mugenda, A.G. (2003). Research methods: Quantitative and qualitative approaches. Nairobi: African Centre for Technology Studies (ACTS Press).
- Nunez, I., & Villanueva, M. (2011). Safety capital: The management of organizational knowledge on occupational health and safety. Journal of Workplace Learning, 23(1), 56-71. Retrieved on January 17th 2018 from <https://doi.org/10.1108/13665621111097254>
- Nzuve, S.N.M., & Njeru, L. K. (2013). Perceived factors affecting performance management among local authorities in Kenya: A case of the city council of Nairobi. DBA Africa Management Review, 3(2), 59-69.

- Nzuve, S.N.M., & Kelwon, S.C. (2014). Attitudes of shop floor employees toward women managers in fuel depots: A case of the fuel depots in Lubumbashi, Democratic Republic of the Congo. *Problems of Management in the 21st Century*, 9(3), 206-212.
- Ruteere, M. (2014). Security and human rights in the new constitutional order in Kenya: The struggle for a new constitutional order (Eds Godwin Murang'a, Duncan Okello, Anders Sjogren). London: Zed Books.
- Shinga, N., & Dyk, G.V. (2015). Factors involved in combat readiness in Africa. A military report. Retrieved on May 28, 2018 from Stellenbosch University.
- Sweden International Development Authority (2013). Strengthening the role of employment injury schemes to help prevent occupational accidents and diseases. The SIDA report, ISBN 978-92-2-127090-4 (print), ISBN 978-92-2-127091-1 (web).
- Tabachnick, B. G., Fidell, L. S., & Ullman, J. B. (2007). *Using multivariate statistics*, Volume 5. Boston, MA: Pearson.
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's Alpha. *International Journal of Medical Education*, 3, 53-55. Retrieved on 7th June 2018 from <https://DOI:10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd>
- Thomson, J. (1997). Employee health programmes: A model designed for a local company. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 9(2), 83-87.
- Transparency International Kenya (2016). Police service satisfaction survey and needs analysis report, 2016: A focus on Kisumu and Nairobi counties. Transparency International Report, Kenya, 1-96.
- Turker, (2015). Police officer willingness to use stress intervention services: The role of perceived organizational support (POS), confidentiality & stigma. *International Journal of Emergency Mental Health and Human Resilience*, 17(1), 304-314. Retrieved on October 13, 2018 from www.digitalcommons.wcupa.edu/crimjustfacpub/4
- Violanti, J. M., Andrew, M. E., Mnatsakanova, A., Hartley, T. A., Fekedulegn, D., & Burchfiel, C. M. (2016). Correlates of hopelessness in the high suicide risk police occupation. *Police Practice and Research*, 17(5), 408-419. Retrieved on October 13th 2018 from <https://doi:10.1080/15614263.2015.1015125>
- Zikmund, W.G., Babin, B.J., Carr, J.C., Adhikari, A., & Griffin, M. (2013). *Business research methods: A south-Asia perspective*, (8th Ed.). New Delhi: Cengage Learning India Pvt. Ltd.